

Introducing a New Audit to Investigate Play Value for Inclusion in Community Playgrounds

Room: W002

Time: Tuesday 6th of June 14:50-15:30

Introducing a New Audit to Investigate Play Value for Inclusion in Community Playgrounds

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Content

- Aim of the workshop
- Introduction participants and research team
- Input
 - Short presentation about the Instrument development up to this point
- Your contribution:
 - Task: Try out part of the audit & reflections
- Collecting reflections

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